

E5.2 First Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for Automated Discovery and SLA Assurance v1.0

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[6GENABLERS-DLT]
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**6G Networks Enabled through
Technology Driven Solutions
[6GENABLERS]**

**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G
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List of Acronyms

6G	Sixth Generation
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DID	Distributed Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
FAMD	Factorial Analysis of Mixed Data
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ID	Identifier
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LLM	Large Language Model
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OAS	OpenAPI Specification
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAM	Random Access Memory
REST	Representational State Transfer
RF	Random Forest
SCSC	Smart Contract State Composer
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SSE	Sum of Squared Errors
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VNF	Virtual Network Function

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable *E5.2 First Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for SLA Assurance*, envisaged in the framework of the project 6GENABLERS-DLT (TSI-063000-2021-12). This deliverable stands as a pioneering achievement within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, aimed at revolutionizing Telecom Marketplaces. This deliverable focuses on the development and implementation of two integral modules within the Smart Discovery system: the Clustering and Classification module and the Intent-based Discovery module. The primary goal of E5.2 is to introduce a prototype of operational components that automate the discovery process within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. By addressing the challenges of complexity, privacy concerns, and stakeholder integration, this deliverable contributes significantly to the broader vision of creating resilient and user-centric Telecom Marketplaces. The document provides a comprehensive exploration of the design specifications, functionalities, architecture, and deployment strategies for both modules. It unfolds a structured narrative, offering insights into the complexities of prototype implementation and establishing a foundation for future advancements. The contributions of E5.2 extend beyond individual modules, envisioning a Telecom Marketplace where stakeholders seamlessly engage with automated, user-friendly, and resilient systems.

1 Introduction

To ensure that future networks align with the diverse needs of applications and users, the paradigm shift towards Telecom Marketplaces necessitates the active involvement of a variety of stakeholders. These stakeholders range from equipment vendors to network operators, cloud and service providers, and application developers. However, the seamless integration of these diverse entities and the facilitation of multipurpose services within a unified environment poses significant challenges. Challenges include heightened operational complexity, as well as concerns related to privacy and trust within the evolving telecommunications landscape.

Addressing these challenges requires the establishment of resilient distributed Marketplaces that enable the effective sharing of network resources and services among stakeholders. Central to this endeavor is the development of automation methods that play a pivotal role in classifying and identifying accessible offers with efficiency and accuracy.

In response to the imperative for resilient and efficient Telecom Marketplaces, the deliverable at hand, E5.2 - "First Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for SLA Assurance," assumes a central role. This deliverable stands as a testament to the commitment of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project in laying the groundwork for a sophisticated and responsive ecosystem.

At its core, this deliverable embodies the initial steps towards the realization of a Smart Discovery system within the broader 6GENABLERS Marketplace – a pivotal outcome of the overarching 6GENABLERS-DLT project. The Smart Discovery system comprises two internal modules: Clustering and Classification and Intent-based Discovery. These modules collectively form a comprehensive toolkit for automated discovery, addressing the intricate challenges associated with diverse network offerings and services.

As we delve into the specifics of E5.2, this document unfolds the intricacies of the prototype implementation, offering insights into the design specifications, functionalities, architecture, and deployment strategies of the Clustering and Classification and Intent-based Discovery modules. By doing so, this deliverable aims to contribute significantly to the evolution of resilient Telecom Marketplaces, where stakeholders can seamlessly engage and leverage network resources while addressing the complexities inherent in the telecommunications landscape.

In summary, E5.2 stands as a pioneering effort within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, envisioning a future where the convergence of stakeholders is harmonized through resilient, automated, and user-centric Telecom Marketplaces. This document serves as a testament to our commitment to innovation and progress in the dynamic realm of distributed ledger technology and telecommunications.

1.1 Document Scope and Objectives

The primary objective of this document is to present and detail the initial prototype for the Smart Discovery system within the 6GENABLERS-DLT research project. This deliverable focuses on outlining the initial prototype implementation of platform

components specifically designed for automated discovery as part of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

The following key aspects define the scope of this document:

This document encompasses the initial prototype implementation of all platform components that play a crucial role in enabling automated discovery within the 6GENABLERS-DLT framework. The scope includes, but is not limited to:

- Development and integration of modules featuring the Smart Discovery system.
- Implementation of interfaces and communication protocols to facilitate seamless interaction between components.
- Inclusion of essential functionalities required for automated discovery processes.

The overarching objectives of this document are as follows:

- 1) **Prototype Implementation:** Provide a comprehensive overview of the initial prototype implementation of platform components of the Smart Discovery system. This involves detailing the development and integration of software modules and components.
- 2) **Functional Specifications:** Present detailed specifications of the functionalities embedded in the prototype, outlining how each component contributes to the automated discovery process. This includes a thorough exploration of data handling, processing, and interaction mechanisms.
- 3) **Documentation:** Deliver supporting documentation that aids users in understanding and effectively utilizing the prototype. This documentation will encompass installation guidelines, operational procedures, and best practices for ensuring seamless integration into diverse environments.
- 4) **Guidelines for Modules:** Offer clear and concise guidelines for the installation and operation of individual modules within the Smart Discovery system. This includes instructions on module-specific configurations and interactions.

By achieving these objectives, this document aims to provide a solid foundation for stakeholders to comprehend, deploy, and utilize the first prototype of operational components and toolkit for automated discovery in the context of the 6GENABLERS-DLT research project.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

This deliverable continues to report the outcomes from Work Package 5 (P5), which covers the pillars related to Smart Discovery and Service Level Agreement (SLA) Assurance. This work package focuses on investigating and developing novel approaches to assist in the discovery and selection of Marketplace offers, accompanied by the monitoring and tracking of SLA terms fulfilment. The goal of this work package is to enrich the 6GENABLERS Marketplace with analytical tools that take customization and flexibility as main guiding principles, to facilitate the identification of available offers, taking into account multiple criteria, and contribute to the monitoring and real-time updates of SLAs status.

As depicted in Figure 1-1, deliverable E5.2 is the joint result of the work done in the two tasks within P5, which are listed below:

Figure 1-1. E5.2 positioning and relation to the project's activities

- A5.1 – Dynamic Resource Discovery: This task focuses on the automated identification and selection of distributed resources from multiple administrative domains. In order to execute selection and ordering of offers for trading settlement, this task is meant to enrich the customer experience when interacting with the Marketplace via advanced and smart strategies to meet searching criteria.
- A5.2 – Proactive SLA Assurance: This task focuses on automating SLA signing underpinned by the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) capabilities. Moreover, it is meant to keep track of contract conditions and Quality of Service (QoS) measurements, ensuring violations are recorded on the ledger, as mechanisms for SLA assurance. Finally, this task will be interlinked to A5.1 in order to trigger the smart discovery of Marketplace offers as a means to avoid potential SLA violations.

Within this context, this document is intended to fulfil the part related to the task A5.1, focused on the Automated Discovery. A similar document will be also generated for the part of SLA Assurance corresponding to the work of task A5.2.

The work captured in this deliverable takes as input the system design reported in the previous deliverable of this task (E5.1 [1]). At the same time, the implementation aspects of the different components to be developed within P5 and provided in this document will feed any required fine-tuning or refinement of the overall 6GENABLERS Marketplace architecture to be reported in the upcoming deliverable E2.3 as part of A2.6 (DLT-anchored Smart Marketplace Architecture).

1.3 Structure of the Document

The current document is structured in several sections to provide a comprehensive understanding of the implementation details of the prototype for the Smart Discovery system. In particular, the document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: This section offers a holistic overview of the document, presenting its objectives, contextualizing its significance within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, and outlining the overall structure.
- Section 2: This section is dedicated to one of the internal modules of the Smart Discovery system, focusing on Clustering and Classification. It delves into its scope and functionalities, architecture, implementation and deployment aspects, as well as the main achieved results and next steps.
- Section 3: Similar to Section 2, this section focuses on the Intent-based Discovery module, providing detailed information on its scope and functionalities, architecture, implementation and deployment aspects, as well as the main achieved results and next steps.
- Section 4: This concluding section synthesizes the main findings, encapsulating the key takeaways from the document.
- Section 5: This section lists the sources and references cited throughout the document as background materials that support and complement the information presented in this deliverable.

2 Clustering and Classification

At the heart of the Smart Discovery system within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace lies the Clustering and Classification module, a sophisticated component designed to bring order to the diverse array of offers available. With a keen focus on enhancing user experience and facilitating seamless interactions, this module incorporates a set of pivotal functionalities that play a crucial role in shaping the landscape of the Telecom Marketplace.

2.1 Scope and Functionalities

As a fundamental part of the Smart Discovery system, a set of functionalities shall be provided by the Clustering and Classification module:

- Pattern's discovery across different types of offers available in the Marketplace. Through this method, the offers available at the Marketplace are categorized according to the patterns identified, which facilitates the identification of various subtypes of elements per offer category.
- New offer classification. This functionality allows the system to efficiently determine the most analogous group for a newly registered offer in the Marketplace, in such a manner that it can be properly identified and searched afterwards when a stakeholder places a new order.
- Cluster discovery from the intent subsystem. This function enables the identification of the most related clusters for an offer that has been previously translated through the intent subsystem.

2.2 Architecture

The software architecture of the Clustering and Classification module is depicted in Figure 2-1. It is composed of three main operational blocks, which are defined in the following subsection.

Figure 2-1. Software architecture of the Clustering and Classification module

2.2.1 Components

As stated in Section 2.1, the Clustering and Classification module provides three differentiated functionalities, which are provided by the following functional entities:

- **Offline pattern identification function (Clustering):** This component is built upon clustering techniques. To achieve this, an offline training process is initially employed to generate several cluster models (one per offer type) on the similarities among the properties of resources within each offer type, resulting in the generation of a set of artificial clusters. To maintain the models' accuracy over time, this process can be periodically repeated, for example, after receiving a specific set of offers or during system maintenance. The training dataset used for the consecutive times the models are trained in includes incoming offers accumulated since the last training session and can be performed in runtime, replacing the current models deployed together in the Marketplace.
- **Online new offer classification function (Classification):** This component utilizes supervised learning techniques, using as input the clustered offers obtained as a labeled dataset from the previous component. The trained model is capable of dynamically categorizing each incoming offer at runtime, assigning it to the appropriate cluster. The identified cluster is then integrated into the stored offer information. Additionally, retraining can be initiated whenever there is an update to the clusters associated with the offers.
- **Online intent request classification function (Intent-proximity):** This component builds on the classification function and uses the same supervised learning model built by that function, to obtain the most similar cluster for the requirements specified by an external user in the intent submitted to the Marketplace. In addition to the previous component, this one also calculates the similarity between the selected cluster and the remaining ones calculated for the same offer type. The objective of this step is to also gather those that have the minimal distance to the selected cluster to provide other alternatives in case of lack of offers availability at that moment in the Marketplace for the most similar cluster.

These functional entities collectively rely on a suite of data structures stored in a database internal to the module, which serves as a repository for data exchange and storage. This repository encompasses essential information concerning, for instance, ML models, datasets, clusters features and standard deviation.

2.2.2 Internal Operational Workflows

This section describes the interactions between the submodules of the Clustering and Classification module. The general interactions are depicted in Figure 2-2, where the main blocks introduced previously in the architecture are included.

In particular, it can be observed that four main operations are considered in the workflow, namely 1) Clustering generation from Marketplace offers; 2) Classification models generation; 3) Classification of new offers at the Marketplace; and 4) Intent proximity computation.

The first operation involves the generation of the new clustering models and their storage, together with a newly labeled dataset including the clusters' information, in the database.

The second operation follows a similar procedure with the aim of generating and storing the random forest models in the database, that will be used in a later stage for incoming offer classification. In these first two operations only the clustering component is involved.

The third block is dedicated to the classification of new offers arriving at the Marketplace. To this end, the classification component gathers the corresponding Random Forest model from the database according to the offer type and returns the computed cluster id for such an offer.

Finally, the operations dedicated to the intent proximity computation involve both the classification component and the intent-proximity component. When a new request is received from the intent component, the classification service deploys the corresponding Random Forest model, which provides the necessary prediction for the cluster id to the intent-proximity component. Depending on the client's requirement to provide one or more cluster ids for having a wider range of options at the Marketplace search, the intent-proximity component will also search for additional clusters as similar as possible to the predicted one and will return their corresponding cluster ids.

Figure 2-2. Internal workflow of the Clustering and Classification module

2.3 Implementation

The main implementation aspects of the Clustering and Classification module are described in this section.

2.3.1 Technologies

The three functional entities described in Section 2.2.1 are developed by leveraging low complexity Machine Learning (ML) models implemented in Python. In particular, the following libraries and specific ML implementations have been selected for each of the three components.

2.3.1.1. Offline pattern identification function

This component is designed to define categories on the marketplace's offers based on their specific characteristics, which are dependent on the type of offer. Initially, clustering methods are utilized to discern patterns within a set of offers sharing similar characteristics due to their common type. For example, features distinguishing slice offers, like access technology, would differ from those characterizing cloud resources, such as Central Processing Unit (CPU) and Random Access Memory (RAM). This initial process occurs offline using a training dataset that encompasses a diverse range of values for features across various offer types.

The first stage involves generating training datasets with approximately 10 000 entries for each one of the offer types (cloud, edge, spectrum, Radio Access Network (RAN), network service, network slice, and Virtual Network Function (VNF)). The libraries used for both preprocessing and training are based on Python. More specifically, for the preprocessing, frameworks like scikit-learn are used to obtain a clean and properly formatted training dataset. Once the dataset is ready, two sub-models are designed and developed: Factorial Analysis of Mixed Data (FAMD) and K-means.

The FAMD algorithm aims to reduce the number of dimensions in a dataset with m variables by using k -principal components. This step is crucial for preparing the dataset for clustering, minimizing the number of clusters needed to group all entries. Unlike a combination of one-hot encoded categorical features and Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which is suitable only for numerical variables, FAMD works with all variable types. It identifies orthogonal components that maximize the projected inertia of all variable types, a task not achieved by PCA. To this end, the Light FAMD Python library [2] is leveraged, properly updated to meet the needs of this project.

Once the dimensionality is reduced, a K-means algorithm partitions each training dataset (one for each offer type) into c clusters. These clusters are characterized by the nearest mean and minimal inner variance, aiding in identifying relationships among offers of the same type. The corresponding cluster is then added to each offer, resulting in a labeled dataset. The determination of the number of clusters for each offer type is computed using the Silhouette method, a coefficient that measures the similarity of data points within a cluster compared to neighboring clusters. This step ensures an optimal and meaningful clustering configuration for each offer type. The K-means algorithm is also based on the scikit-learn Python library [3].

2.3.1.2. Online new offer classification function

This model is designed to function as an online tool for classifying offers within the Marketplace. In other words, the ML model is responsible for dynamically assigning a cluster to incoming offers in real-time. However, these offers are initially represented by the original features from the training datasets. To ensure a human-readable classification, the features of the datasets are reversed from principal components to the original features before training, while preserving the cluster labels.

For the classification process, a Random Forest (RF) model is employed as a supervised ML model. RF is an ensemble learning algorithm that ensures high accuracy and precision by utilizing a set of decision trees. In this case, the depth of the decision trees is limited to prevent overfitting. Each tree in the ensemble is trained with a subset of observations, and the leaf node of each tree outputs a specific cluster C (belonging to that offer type).

The final selection of the cluster follows a majority-voting approach. It is important to note that a separate RF model is trained for each offer type, and these ML models are validated using additional datasets containing 1000 entries for each one. The Random Forest model is built using the H2O Python library [4], which permits the implementation of these models supporting both categorical and numerical variables.

2.3.1.3. Online intent request classification function

As stated in Section 2.2.1, this component follows the same procedure as the previous one responsible for new offers classification.

When a new intent request is translated by the Intent-based Discovery module as a result of a user search, this component composes the skeleton of the whole offer and requests the new offer classification function to provide the most suitable cluster for that offer type. This cluster identifier (ID) is then used to gather from the Trading DLT the available offers that have been previously registered and classified with the same cluster id.

However, there could be situations where no offers are present at that moment for that cluster id. For those cases, this function also looks for the two closest clusters to the selected one, with the aim of having a wider variety of offer possibilities to be provided to the users, which are given sorted from the greatest to the lowest similarity.

To do so, this function computes the Manhattan distance between the coordinates of the classified cluster ID (in FAMD form) and the coordinates of the rest of the clusters of the same offer type, selecting those with the minimal distance. This distance is computed as per the Manhattan distance as follows: $\sum_i |a_i - b_i|$, where a_i represents the coordinates of the classified cluster ID, and b_i refers to the coordinates of the rest of the clusters computed for that offer type.

2.3.1.4. Local database for internal storage

For information storing, the Clustering and Classification module relies on a MongoDB database. In particular, several associations are created and used in the database. The management of the data is performed as described in the operations detailed in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1. Database relationship on the Clustering and Classification module

Name	Description	Data type	Operations
cc-sl-data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains a set of collections, one per each offer category. - Each collection contains a labeled dataset generated for each type of offer. The labeled dataset includes the clean version of the training dataset and an additional column for the computed cluster. 	Tables, Structured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The clustering service populates this data and updates it when clusters are generated. - When the random forest models are generated, this data is used for training and validation purposes.
cc-models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains a set of collections, one per each offer category. - Each collection contains the clustering and classification ML models generated for each type of offer. 	Bytes, Unstructured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The clustering service populates this data and updates it when the clusters are regenerated. - When receiving a new offer or a new intent for cluster retrieval, this data is used to gather the required classification ML model according to the offer type.
cc-clusters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains a set of collections, one per each offer category. - Each collection contains a table showing, as many rows as the number of clusters identified, and as many columns as the number of features used to create the clusters. - Each cell in the table represents the centroid of the cluster (average of all the points contained in the cluster) for a given cluster number and feature. 	Tables, Structured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The clustering service populates this data and updates it when the clusters are regenerated.
cc-clusters-dev	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains a set of collections, one per each offer category. - Each collection contains a table showing, as many rows as the number of clusters identified, and as many columns as the number of features used to create the clusters. - Each cell in the table represents the average deviation of the cluster for a given cluster number and feature (computed as the average deviation between each point contained with respect to the centroid). 	Tables, Structured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The clustering service populates this data and updates it when the clusters are regenerated.
cc-predicted-offers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains a set of collections, one per each offer category. - Each collection contains the identifier of the processed offer plus the cluster number on which it has been 	Json files, Structured data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The classification service adds a data entry every time a new offer gets classified.

	classified.		
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2.3.2 Data model

The main data model used for this module is dedicated to representing the offer information. To do so, the considered data model is based in the Product Offering data model specified by TM Forum [5]. Using this schema as base, an all-in-one data model is produced for the 6GENABLERS Marketplace offers, which contains all the indispensable child entities such as Category [6], Place [7], Product Offering Price [8], Product Specification [9], Resource Specification [10] and SLA [11].

This all-in-one offer data model follows a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format with common fields across all offer types, as shown in Figure 2-3. In particular, the following fields can be observed:

- *Category*. This list of dictionaries contains the information of the offer type, given by the name of the offer type itself and a short description.
- *Description*. String that provides a description of the specific offer.
- *Name*. String specifying the name of the specific offer.
- *Place*. This field is common to all offer types, except for the resources related to network service and virtual network function. It is represented by a list of dictionaries, containing each of them four keys, namely “city”, “country”, “geographicLocation” and “locality”. The keys city, country and locality are simple strings regarding the physical location of the concrete resource. By contrast, the field geographic location is a dictionary, containing the name of the location (a combination a city and country), and the geometry, which is a dictionary with the exact coordinates of the resource place.
- *Product offering price*. This field is represented by a list of dictionaries, each of them containing the information of a specific price given to the resource. Each dictionary contains description and name. Moreover, the price field provides through a dictionary the value of the price and the currency. In addition to this, the field “priceType” is a string that can take different values according to the followed price model (e.g. recurring, one time). When this field is set to “one time”, no additional fields are provided, since the payment is performed only once. However, when this field is set to “recurring”, two additional fields must be provided, namely “recurringChargePeriodLenght” (which provides via a numerical value the charging period) and “recurringChargePeriodType” (which specifies how often the payment is performed).
- *Product specification*. This dictionary contains the specific characteristics of each offer type and is particular to each type. Nonetheless, they all contain a description and a name of the product specification. The dictionary also contains a list named “resourceSpecification”, which hosts the fields “description”, “feature”, and “name”, and a list named “resourceSpecCharacteristic”, which contains a dictionary for each of the features corresponding to the offer. Notice that is not necessary that all offers display the range of features contained in a type, and that at least one feature is mandatory.

```

{
  "category": [
    {
      "description": "Network Slice",
      "name": "Network Slice"
    }
  ],
  "description": "Sample Network Slice Offer",
  "name": " Sample Network Slice Offer",
  "place": [
    {
      "city": "Barcelona",
      "country": "Spain",
      "geographicLocation": {
        "geometry": [
          {
            "x": 41.3879,
            "y": 2.1699,
            "z": 0
          }
        ],
        "name": "Barcelona, Spain"
      },
      "locality": "Barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "productOfferingPrice": [
    {
      "description": "Sample POP description",
      "name": "Sample POP name",
      "price": {
        "unit": "EUR",
        "value": 3200
      },
      "priceType": "Recurring",
      "recurringChargePeriodLength": 1,
      "recurringChargePeriodType": "yearly"
    }
  ],
  "productSpecification": {
    "description": "Sample Product Specification description",
    "name": " Sample Product Specification name",
    "resourceSpecification": [
      {
        "description": " Sample Resource Specification description",
        "feature": [],
        "name": " Sample Resource Specification name",
        "resourceSpecCharacteristic": [

```

Figure 2-3. Common structure of the data model for all offer types

The specific characteristics included in the “resourceSpecCharacteristic” list are shown below for each type of offer.

In particular, in Figure 2-4 and Figure 2-5 the characteristics for the network slice resource can be found. As can be seen, there are a maximum of seven characteristics that this type of offer can accommodate.

The features “Maximum Downlink throughput per network slice” and “Maximum Uplink throughput per network slice” defines the maximum throughput expected on the network slice for downlink and uplink traffic. As all features, this dictionary contains a name and a list called “resourceSpecCharacteristicValue”, which for these two features is given by a list of dictionaries containing “unitOfMeasure” (in this case, given any measure acceptable for throughput like kbps) and “value” (indicating the specific value of the unit given before). In addition to this, four more features share the same structure among themselves, being it a dictionary containing the characteristic name,

and a list of “resourceSpecCharacteristicValue”. These four characteristics are “Isolation level” (describing the slice isolation, and which can be set to “Logical Isolation” or “Physical Isolation”), “Data network access” (describing the status of the data network, and which can take the values: “Termination in the private network”, “Direct internet access”, and “Local traffic (no internet access)”), “Access technology” (describing the type of radio access, and being set to “4G” or “5G”), and “Area of service” (the area from which the resource is served). The “Radio spectrum” follows the same structure, but adds a field named “configurable”, a boolean specifying if modifications are allowed in the radio channel value.

```

{
  "name": "Maximum Downlink throughput per network slice",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "kbps",
      "value": {
        "value": 20000000
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Maximum Uplink throughput per network slice",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "kbps",
      "value": {
        "value": 100000
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Isolation level",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "Logical Isolation"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Data network access",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "Termination in the private network"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Access technology",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "4G"
      }
    }
  ]
},

```

Figure 2-4. Resource specification characteristics for network slice offers (1)

```

{
  "name": "Area of service",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "Hong Kong"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "configurable": false,
  "name": "Radio spectrum",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 39
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 2-5. Resource specification characteristics for network slice offers (2)

The data model related to the network service offers is depicted in Figure 2-6 and Figure 2-7, which can take up to four different features. The first one, named “service type” follows the same structure as the one described for the network slice offers, and specifies the type of network service that is being offered. Example of this feature includes holo_comms, UPF, CDN, etc.

The three remaining features named “vCPU Requirements”, “Virtual Memory Requirements” and “Storage Requirements” follow, however, a different structure from the rest. In this case, the “resourceSpecCharacteristicValue” list contains two dictionaries with the aim of defining one for the minimum value required and the other for the maximum value.

```

{
  "name": "service type",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "UPF"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "vCPU Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "alias": "min-vCPU",
        "value": 3
      }
    },
    {
      "value": {
        "alias": "max-vCPU",
        "value": 6
      }
    }
  ]
},

```

Figure 2-6. Resource specification characteristics for network service offers (1)

```

{
  "name": "Virtual Memory Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "min-virtual-memory",
        "value": 24000
      }
    },
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "max-virtual-memory",
        "value": 24000
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "Storage Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "min-storage",
        "value": 380
      }
    },
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "max-storage",
        "value": 380
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 2-7. Resource specification characteristics for network service offers (2)

For instance, for the case of vCPU, the first dictionary contains an alias (“min-vCPU”) and another field with the value for such an alias. The second dictionary has the same structure for the maximum value. For the case of virtual memory and storage requirements, a new field is added to each dictionary within the list named “unitOfMeasure”, which indicates the measure of the value specified (e.g., “GB” for the storage case).

Conversely, an example of the data model for the VNF offer type can be seen in Figure 2-8. VNFs can be defined by a total of four distinct characteristics, namely “function type”, “vCPU Requirements”, “Virtual Memory Requirements” and “Storage Requirements”.

As it can be observed, the structure followed by the VNFs is the same to the ones of the network services offers (sharing “vCPU Requirements”, “Virtual Memory Requirements”, and “Storage Requirements”) except for the “service type” feature. This feature is replaced in VNFs by a new characteristic called “function type”, which describes the type of virtual network function being requested by the end user. Example values include CDN, UPF, firewall, xr_player, dpi, NAT, etc.

```

    {
      "name": "function type",
      "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "value": {
            "value": "CDN"
          }
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "vCPU Requirements",
      "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "value": {
            "alias": "min-vCPU",
            "value": 7
          }
        },
        {
          "value": {
            "alias": "max-vCPU",
            "value": 7
          }
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "Virtual Memory Requirements",
      "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
          "value": {
            "alias": "min-virtual-memory",
            "value": 16064
          }
        },
        {
          "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
          "value": {
            "alias": "max-virtual-memory",
            "value": 16064
          }
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "Storage Requirements",
      "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
          "value": {
            "alias": "min-storage",
            "value": 320
          }
        },
        {
          "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
          "value": {
            "alias": "max-storage",
            "value": 640
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 2-8. Resource specification characteristics for VNF offers

The data model for cloud and edge offers have the same structure, as can be seen in the examples in Figure 2-9 and Figure 2-10. Both offer types share three specific characteristics, namely “cpu”, “memory” and “storage”.

```

{
  "name": "cpu",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 20
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "memory",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "value": 126976
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "storage",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "value": 1060
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 2-9. Resource specification characteristics for cloud offers

```

{
  "name": "cpu",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 2
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "memory",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "value": 11776
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "storage",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "value": 10
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 2-10. Resource specification characteristics for edge offers

Each of these characteristics is defined by a “resourceSpecCharacteristicValue” list of dictionaries. For each dictionary, two fields are given: “unitOfMeasure” (which indicates the unit in which the characteristic is requested) and “value”. The main distinction is the range of values that each offer type can take, since edge resources have lower limits than their counterparts in the cloud.

On the other hand, RAN offers count with eight features that can be included in the Marketplace, namely “ranType”, “txPower”, “bandwidth”, “duplexMode”, “technology”, “operationBand”, “centralDLFrequency” and “centralULFrequency”. An example of this offer type is depicted in Figure 2-11 and Figure 2-12.

```

{
  "name": "ranType",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "cell"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "txPower",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "W",
      "value": {
        "value": 48
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "bandwidth",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 10
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "duplexMode",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "FDD"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "technology",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "5G"
      }
    }
  ]
},
},

```

Figure 2-11. Resource specification characteristics for RAN offers (1)

```

{
  "name": "operationBand",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 3
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "centralDLFrequency",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 1810
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "centralULFrequency",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 1715
      }
    }
  ]
}
}

```

Figure 2-12. Resource specification characteristics for RAN offers (2)

As can be seen, the features called “ranType” (describing either if it is a cell or an access point), “duplexMode” (providing information about the modulation and multiplexing mode), “technology” (specifying either if the radio type refers to 4G, 5G or Wi-Fi 6), and “operationBand” (giving the network band for the radio access) have the same structure. More specifically, the first key of the dictionary sets the name, while the second one (the “resourceSpecCharacteristicValue” list) provides a nested dictionary containing just the value expected for the feature. By contrast, in the case of the features named “txPower” (specifying the transmission power), “bandwidth” (setting the network bandwidth of the radio segment), “centralDLFrequency” (providing the downlink frequency band), “centralULFrequency” (providing the uplink frequency band) a new key is added to the dictionary included in the “resourceSpecCharacteristicValue” list to specify the “unitOfMeasure” of the characteristics. Notice that the first group does not contain this key since those features are dimensionless.

Finally, the spectrum offers count with seven different features that can be specified, as shown in Figure 2-13 and Figure 2-14.

```

{
  "name": "duplexMode",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "TDD"
      }
    }
  ]
},

```

Figure 2-13. Resource specification characteristics for spectrum offers (1)

```

{
  "name": "operationBand",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 78
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "technology",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": "5G"
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "startFreqDl",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 3650
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "endFreqDl",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 3675
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "startFreqUl",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 3650
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "endFreqUl",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MHz",
      "value": {
        "value": 3675
      }
    }
  ]
}
}

```

Figure 2-14. Resource specification characteristics for spectrum offers (2)

In particular, the features “duplexMode”, “operationBand” and “technology” are identical to the ones described for the RAN offers. In this case, four different characteristics are defined for spectrum, sharing all the same structure stated before in this document (i.e., a dictionary containing value and unit of measure) as follows: “startFreqDL” (providing the starting frequency for downlink traffic), “endFreqDL” (setting the end frequency for downlink traffic), “startFreqUL” (noting the starting frequency for uplink traffic) and “endFreqUL” (describing the end frequency for uplink traffic).

2.3.3 Interfaces

The Clustering and Classification module exposes an Application Programming Interface (API). The involved Representational State Transfer (REST) endpoints are based on OpenAPI specification (OAS).

2.3.3.1 Exposed

The endpoints exposed by this module API can be seen in the OpenAPI shown in Figure 2-15. In particular, three big groups of endpoints, exposed through REST API methods, can be distinguished: cluster generation, offer prediction and intent cluster proximity.

The cluster generation group contains a single POST method named “/clusters_generation”, which enables the creation of the ML models necessary for the clusters corresponding to the offline pattern identification function, as well as of the random forest ML models to be used for the online offer classification function. Through this method, the synthetic clusters for the offer type specified by the user are generated, in such a manner that a new cleaned and labelled dataset is created and stored in the local database. The cluster generation also involves the cleaning and preprocessing of the original training file to remove unnecessary features, adjust the input format for the algorithm, etc. This labelled dataset is then used as input for the creation of the random forest models.

Figure 2-15. Exposed OpenAPI of the Clustering and Classification module

Figure 2-16 depicts an example of the input schema for the POST /clusters_generation endpoint, which takes essentially three arguments: mode, training_dataset_path, and offer_type.

```

Example Value | Schema
{
  "mode": "process_dataset|ul_kmeans|ul_famd_kmeans|sl_random_forest",
  "training_dataset_path": "datasets/training_dataset.json",
  "offer_type": "spectrum"
}

```

Figure 2-16. Example schema of the POST /clusters_generation endpoint

The mode parameter can take four possible values, namely “process_dataset” (which only cleans and prepares the dataset to be used by the clustering methods), “ul_kmeans” (which generates unsupervised k-means models in case of having a dataset with only numerical variables), “ul_famd_kmeans” (which first creates a FAMD dimensionality reduction for any variable type and then generates the necessary k-means models), and “sl_random_forest” (which creates the random forest models for classification taking as a reference the already labelled dataset from the k-means model, a reason why this method cannot be used without a k-means model in place). Both the cleaned datasets and the generated models are stored in the database as described in Section 2.2.1. Conversely, the training dataset requires specifying the path where the original dataset is placed. Finally, the offer type argument can take as input any specific offer type (e.g., cloud) or left empty. In this last case, the component will generate the models for all the available offer types in the dataset provided.

As shown in Figure 2-15, the Offer Prediction group contains four different methods: POST “offer_prediction”, GET “offer_prediction”, GET “offer_prediction/{offer_id}” and DELETE “offer_prediction/{offer_id}”. The POST “offer_prediction” classifies a new incoming offer into a specific synthetic cluster defined within its offer type and stores this mapping of offer Distributed Identifier (DID) and cluster ID in the local database. The input of this endpoint is a new offer, according to the all-in-one data model described in Section 2.3.2. Notice that only one resource characteristic is mandatory to be provided. The GET “offer_prediction” method, which takes no input parameters, provides a list of dictionaries, containing for each of the classified offers the “offer_id” and the corresponding “cluster_id” that was assigned when registering the offer. An example can be observed in Figure 2-17.

```

[
  {
    "offer_id": "string",
    "cluster_id": "1"
  }
]

```

Figure 2-17. Output of the GET /offer_prediction endpoint

A similar functionality is provided by the GET “offer_prediction/{offer_id}”, which returns the same information of the previously described method, but for a specific offer identifier. For that reason, the output is just a dictionary indicating the cluster identifier by which it was classified. Finally, the DELETE “offer_prediction/{offer_id}” method deletes a specific offer from the local record of classified offers given by its offer identifier.

The last group of endpoints has a single method named POST “intent_cluster_proximity”. This method is solely used by the Intent-based Discovery module when an end-user requests any resource via an intent to the Marketplace.

Once the intent-based method translates the user request, this method can be called, to predict the cluster or clusters more similar to the user request, as described in Section 2.2.1. An example of the input is displayed in Figure 2-18.

```
Example Value | Schema
{
  "offer": [
    {
      "parameter_name": "cpu",
      "parameter_value": "3"
    }
  ],
  "offer_type": "cloud",
  "various_clusters": false
}
```

Figure 2-18. Example of input for the POST /intent_cluster_proximity endpoint

As can be seen, three mandatory fields must be present, namely the offer itself (which is a list of dictionaries, containing for each of them the parameter name and value of the specified features), the offer type, and the wish to find one or more clusters matching the user's request.

2.3.3.2 Consumed

The Clustering and Classification module does not consume any interfaces. This module does not call the interface of any other component within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

2.4 Deployment

The developed code for the Clustering and Classification module is available in the project repository (hosted in Gitlab). In this section, the main deployment aspects to get this application running are provided.

2.4.1 Installation Procedures

The component is provided together with a Dockerfile that specifies the requirements to be installed and any other dependencies of modules and volumes that must be installed and deployed before the component itself. The default ports required by all the involved applications are specified in this file and match the ones in the project config file (/conf/config.cfg). In the case of changes, the configuration file should be also updated. These dependencies included java version 11, graphviz and graphviz-dev, python 3.8 and pip >= 21.0.1. Moreover, a docker compose file is also provided for the joint deployment of the python application with the required MongoDB database.

For the specific containerised deployment in Kubernetes, a yaml file is provided with the required resource definitions. This file includes the specifications of a deployment to manage the application lifecycle, a service of type NodePort to expose the application API in the cluster, and two secrets containing the registry credentials to pull the application image and the application configuration file.

2.4.2 User Documentation

For the configuration and training of the ML models, a set of steps must be performed as follows:

- Edit the config.cfg file in /conf directory to adjust all configuration values. The configuration file includes settings related to the server, the data preprocessing of the training dataset (including the default path to such dataset), the FAMD and k-means model, the random forest model, and the databases used.
- As stated before, the models must be generated in a certain order since dependencies exist among them. The process to be completed is as follows:
 - First the POST /clusters_generation endpoint must be executed taking as input the “ul_famd_kmeans” mode. Notice that this call already involves the data preprocessing. The generated labelled dataset is stored in the cc-sl-data database. In the config.cfg file related to the generation of this model, the following parameters outlined in Table 2-2 shall be taken into account.

Table 2-2. Configuration parameter values for the clusters’ generation (1)

Conf. Parameter	Values	Description
del_outliers	True	K-means is very sensible to present outliers and must be removed.
feature_scaling	SCALING_NO (0)	The FAMD library performs its own internal scaling process.
categorical_features	ENCODING_NO (0)	The FAMD library can handle categorical and numeric classes.
class_feature	None	K-means, as unsupervised learning method, has no feature class.

- Once the cluster generation has finished successfully, the second step involves generating the random forest models with the aim of classifying new incoming offers to be registered in the Marketplace and that could be partially completed in terms of features. To this end, the POST /clusters_generation endpoint must be executed taking as input the “sl_random_forest” mode. This model retrieves the information required for training from the cc-sl-data database. Once generated, this mode creates the random forest models and place them at the cc-models database. The algebraical design of this method imposes as mandatory the following configuration outlined in Table 2-3 in the config.cfg file.

Table 2-3. Configuration parameter values for the clusters’ generation (2)

Conf. Parameter	Values	Description
del_outliers	True	As good practice outliers can be revised again.
feature_scaling	SCALING_NO (0)	Random forest does not need prior scaling processes.
categorical_features	ENCODING_NO (0)	The library handles categorical and numeric classes.
class_feature	'cluster'	It takes the clusters selected by clustering methods as main class.

- At this stage, the system is ready to classify any incoming offer that shall be registered in the Marketplace in real-time. To do so, the POST “offer_prediction” endpoint is used, setting as input body the information of the offer to be registered. Consequently, the offer is properly classified and registered in the

Marketplace and is ready for any call received from the Intent-based Discovery module when a new search request is set by a user.

- Finally, at this point, any translated request from the intent discovery module can be searched at the marketplace computing the most suitable clusters depending on the characteristics provided for the offer request. To this end, the POST “intent_cluster_proximity” can be called, providing as input the schema shown in Figure 2-18.

2.4.3 Integration Guideline

This module is consumed by the Offering API and by the Intent-based Discovery module for the following purposes:

- Integration with the Offering API: When a new offer arrives to the Marketplace, it is received by the Smart Contract State Composer (SCSC), which delegates the offer to the Offering API. In turn, the Offering API interacts with the Clustering and Classification module of the Smart Discovery system to consume its Classification endpoint. This integration results in the determination of a cluster ID for the incoming offer, which is returned to the Offering API for its storage into the Trading DLT.
- Integration with the Intent-based Discovery module: This is an interaction internal to the operational flows of the Smart Discovery system. When a discovery request is submitted to the Marketplace, this is received by the SCSC, which forwards it to the Intent-based Discovery module of the Smart Discovery system. Then, the Intent-based Discovery module translate the received intent by identifying the requested offer type and attributes. With this information, the Intent-based Discovery module triggers the Intent-proximity endpoint of the Clustering and Classification module to retrieve in response the clusters ID that correspond to the user intent.

2.5 Results and Next Steps

In this document we have provided a detailed description of the Clustering and Classification module. To this end, a K-means and Random Forest models have been designed, developed and deployed for each of the seven resource offer types that can be registered at the Marketplace.

In Table 2-4, we provide details of the k-means results obtained for each type of offer. In this regard, the following number of clusters have been identified for each offer type, together with the Sum of Squared Errors (SSE).

Table 2-4. Results of the k-means clustering model

Offer type	Cloud	Edge	Network Service	Network Slice	VNF	Spectrum	RAN
# clusters	5	5	7	4	10	5	8
SSE	501.12	147.78	1443.54	69.08	1.21	0.000006	0.000002

In view of the previous results, where we can appreciate differences in the error rate depending on the offer type, the next steps will involve the revision of the three first

offers type (i.e., cloud, edge and network service) models with the aim of improving the model accuracy and reducing the error performed.

Conversely, for the random forest classification the results obtained in terms of accuracy with respect to the predicted cluster is as presented in Table 2-5, reporting on the mean per-class error (which identifies the number of times an offer has been classified with a certain cluster by mistake).

Table 2-5. Results of the random forest classification model

Offer type	Cloud	Edge	Network Service	Network Slice	VNF	Spectrum	RAN
Mean per-class error	0.006	0.003	0.032	0.006	0.049	0.006	0.002

From the data, it can be seen that the error rate from the random forest models does not reach 1% in the worst case, and therefore, the accuracy for the new offers classification is high enough.

3 Intent-based Discovery

Within the intricacies of the Smart Discovery system, the Intent-based Discovery module emerges as a visionary component designed to bridge the gap between user intent and the wealth of offerings within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This module operates as a key enabler, translating user intentions expressed in natural language into a structured syntactic form. Its overarching objective is to enhance user interaction by offering a seamless and intuitive means of navigating the diverse Telecom Marketplace.

3.1 Scope and Functionalities

The Intent-based Discovery module unfolds a set of functionalities finely tuned to interpret and respond to user intent in a manner that optimally aligns with the offerings available in the Marketplace:

- **Intent Translation from Natural Language.** At the core of its capabilities, this module excels in translating received intents from natural language expressions to a predefined syntactic structure. This structure encapsulates essential elements, including the type of offer and the specific characteristics requested by the user.
- **Cluster Retrieval for Aligned Intent.** Building upon the translated intent, the Intent-based Discovery module further orchestrates the retrieval of the cluster that best aligns with the user's expressed preferences. By identifying the most relevant cluster, the module ensures that the subsequent recommendations and offers are tailored to the user's underlying requirements.
- **Offer Retrieval Corresponding to the Indicated Cluster.** The final functionality of this module revolves around retrieving the set of offers registered in the Marketplace that corresponds to the indicated cluster. Once the optimal cluster is identified, the system efficiently retrieves the catalog of offers associated with that specific cluster. This ensures that users are presented with a curated selection that precisely matches their expressed intent, streamlining the process of discovering and selecting offerings.

3.2 Architecture

The software architecture of the Intent-based Discovery module is depicted in Figure 3-1. It is composed of different internal components, which are defined in the following subsection.

Figure 3-1. Software architecture of the Intent-based Discovery module

3.2.1 Components

Figure 3-1 shows all the components and its relation within the Intent-based Discovery module.

- The API is the entry point for the intent-based discovery and provides an interface to execute remote operations regarding offer retrieval.
- The database client is used to interact with the intent-discovery database. This database stores a historic of the executed intents and its retrieved offers.
- The intent engine performs all the internal logic and acts as a controller for the different components. The intent processing logic is modelled as a finite state machine, and it is described in detail in Section 3.
- In order to perform some operations such as natural language translation or the offer retrieval given a set of attributes, southbound clients are used. The available southbound clients are:
 - The LLM client is responsible for sending a prompt to the pre-trained LLM server so it can translate the intent into a “*semi-natural*” intent that can be later processed by the intent engine’s finite state machine.
 - The cluster classifier client has the single responsibility of sending the attributes from the introduced intent to the Clustering and Classification module and provide back the cluster identifier.
 - Finally, the DLT client is responsible for retrieving offers from the blockchain through the Offering API by using the cluster identified previously gotten by the cluster classifier.

3.2.2 Internal Operational Workflows

The main workflow is when a user introduces a natural language (or semi-natural) intent into the Intent-based Discovery API, and it returns a set of available offers related to that specific intent.

Figure 3-2 shows a high-level workflow of the interactions pictured in Figure 3-1. First, the entry point of the Intent-based Discovery is the API. The intent is first introduced via POST operation in the `/intent` endpoint, passing the `raw_intent` and the language flag (that can be either `semi_natural` or `natural`). The API supports two types of intent: *natural* and *semi natural* language. We refer to *semi natural* language a sentence formed with the following structure:

```
<action> <resource> [<preposition or connector> <keyword argument> ... <preposition or connector> <keyword argument> ...]
```

For example:

```
Discover offers for offer_type=cloud with price=300, memory=2GB, cpu=3, storage=500GB and location=Madrid
```

The *natural* language approach offers a more flexible way to write intents. For example, the previous intent would look like:

```
I would like to retrieve offers for a cloud service with 2GB of memory, 500GB of storage, at least 3 cpus, located in Madrid and with a price of maximum 300€
```

However, whereas the *natural* translation approach offers a more flexible way of processing intents, it relies on a non-deterministic Large Language Model (LLM) that may not probably guess completely right the user's intent. On the other hand, the *semi-natural* language offers a deterministic approach for translating the intent, but the user is constrained for the way that sentences are written.

Once the *raw* intent has been received, it is passed to the intent engine, and it instantiates a finite state machine in order to start processing the intent. If the intent is written in natural language (i.e., it has the *natural* argument set by the user) then it is first sent to an LLM server to process the intent and it returns the intent parsed in *semi-natural* language. Then, the finite state machine starts processing the intent in *semi-natural* language, extracting the arguments, and sending the necessary payload for the Clustering and Classification module. Then, the Clustering and Classification module determines the corresponding cluster for the given fields, and then the finite state machine queries the blockchain through the Offering API in order to retrieve the set of offers that are located within the given cluster. Finally, this response is returned in a JSON serialized format to the user through an Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) response.

Figure 3-2. Internal workflow of the Intent-based Discovery module

3.3 Implementation

The main implementation aspects of the Intent-based Discovery module are described in this section.

3.3.1 Technologies

The library used for implementing finite state machines is called `pytransitions` [12]. It is a python library designed for building finite state machines in a simple, but yet efficient way. It provides an intuitive interface to define states, transitions and associated actions, making it easy to model and manage the behavior of systems with discrete states and transitions, as happens with the processing of the intent.

The API is implemented in the well-known python backend framework `FastAPI` [13]. `FastAPI` is a modern, fast, web framework for building APIs with Python. It is designed to be easy to use, efficient, and to leverage the capabilities of the latest Python features. `FastAPI` takes advantage of type annotations to automatically generate `OpenAPI` and `JSON Schema` documentation, allowing for a seamless development process. It is asynchronous by default, using the power of Python's `asyncio` [14] to handle concurrent operations efficiently. `FastAPI` also incorporates automatic validation, dependency injection, and serialization, making it a robust and developer-friendly choice for building scalable and performant web APIs.

The project is organized in Python packages that are grouped by functionality. The code is organized as follows:

- The `api` package. This module handles the API functionality. It contains the dependencies management of the API, i.e., the intent engine; the endpoints of the API inside the `routers` module. Finally, the `schemas` module includes the `pydantic` classes that are used for data validation in the API.

- The *clients* package. It contains the implementations of the clients that interact with remote components: the Offering API, the Clustering and Classification module and the LLM server.
- The *db* package. It contains the database implementations used by the Intent-based Discovery. For the sake of simplicity, so far, the only database available is an in-memory database implemented as a hash map, i.e., a Python dictionary. However, relying solely on an in-memory database is not always ideal due to its lack of persistence. To address this, the database instantiation employs a factory pattern. This pattern effectively separates the database implementation from the interactions facilitated by the Intent-based Discovery API, ensuring greater flexibility and decoupling in the overall design.
- The *intent_engine* package is the core of the implementation. It acts as a controller for passing objects between the different internal components. Inside of that package there are a few relevant components:
 - The *fsm* package contains the logic of the transitions of the finite state machine, as well as the implementations of the states.
 - The *Intent* class models an intent object and all the arguments related to it.

3.3.1.1 Finite State Machine

As stated in previous sections, the core logic of the Intent-based Discovery module is modelled and implemented as a state machine. Finite states machines work well in modeling systems with discrete states and transitions. Also, they provide a clear and intuitive way to represent the behavior of systems that can be in a finite number of states and transition between them based on input events. Furthermore, the library used to implement finite state machines, *pytransitions* [12], also allows us to execute callbacks when the state machine enters some state, as well as to trigger transitions according to some conditions.

To that end, Figure 3-3 shows the diagram of the finite state machine that the intent engine uses to process the intents.

The first transition is a conditional transition. If the user had introduced an intent written in natural language, then the *is_semi_natural_lang* flag will be set to *false* and then the next state will be *natural_intent_translation*. Otherwise, the next state will be *semi_natural_intent_translation*. In the *natural_intent_translation* state, the *enter* callback will invoke the LLM client and perform a query to the LLM server in order to get a *semi-natural* language intent back. Later, the state machine will move to the *semi_natural_intent_translation* and will extract the relevant arguments to later on move to the *intent_cluster_retrieval* state. Once there, the *enter* callback will invoke the cluster classifier client and will retrieve the relevant cluster for the given arguments. Next, in the *offers_retrieval* state, the callback will invoke the DLT client and will return the relevant offers for the given cluster. Finally, some sorting of the offers will be done in the *offers_sorting* state if needed and then the intent will be moved to its final state *intent_enforced*.

Figure 3-3. Finite state machine implemented at the Intent-based Discovery module

3.3.1.2 Large Language Models for Intent Processing

In order to implement the intent processing, i.e., translate a *natural* intent into a *semi-natural* one, we have deployed and inferred an LLM. The motivation behind using an LLM is the low barrier to infer a general purpose LLM to be an intent interpreter. However, despite the ease of inference of LLMs to be used as an intent interpreter for the use case described in previous sections, running LLMs is computationally expensive both in terms of training, inference and even prompt execution. Natural Language Processing (NLP) mechanisms are commonly used in intent processing tasks like chatbots, virtual assistants, and automated customer support systems. However, they require context understanding provided by large datasets. With very minimal datasets, it is difficult to get accurate results and outperform LLMs. All in all, we decided to go for LLMs due to the easiness of fine-tuning for intent processing and decent performance.

In order to have a stand-alone solution and being concerned about data privacy regarding managing potential sensitive information within the intent processing, we decided to deploy a self-hosted open-source LLM. The model of choice has been Mistral [15], an open-source large language model distributed with the apache license. It outperforms llama 2 on several benchmarks [15] and we noted it performs quite good at the intent processing task.

The model is run under ollama [16], a framework that allows to run and fine-tune LLMs locally as well as expose an API to perform remote operations, such as fine-tune a

model or submit a prompt. The model runs on a VM with 8 GB of RAM, 4 vCPUs Intel Xeon Processor (Cascadelake) and 60 GB of disk. However, the most important resource is to let ollama use GPU to process prompts, otherwise CPU usage easily peaks to 100% and the latency to process a prompt becomes really high. However, with GPU capabilities enabled, the LLM makes use of the GPU, and the CPU usage is almost negligible. The used GPU is a Nvidia Tesla T4 with 16GB of memory. Although the LLM is answering considerably fast to the initial tests, we cannot tell by now how well it scales if several users are querying the model at the same time.

3.3.2 Data model

In order to submit an intent, the API exposes an HTTP POST method that accepts two parameters: the *raw_intent*, of type *string*, and the *language*, of type *literal* (only takes two values: *natural* and *semi_natural*).

The main data model used for this module is dedicated to representing the intent object. The intent object contains all the state information, which is composed while the intent is being processed. The *Intent* class has the following arguments:

- *raw_intent*: The raw intent introduced by the user in plain text.
- *is_semi_natural*: A boolean that indicates weather the intent is written in natural or semi-natural language.
- *action*: Verb of the intent.
- *resource*: Resource or noun of the intent.
- *intent_engine*: Pointer to the *IntentEngine* objects, which acts as a controller. That way, other components can access the attributes of the *Intent* object through the intent engine.
- *args*: A generic list of keyword arguments.
- *id*: Unique identifier that represents the intent.
- *status*: Enum that indicates the status of the intent.
- *offers*: Array of offers related to intent.

3.3.3 Interfaces

As described before, the Intent-based Discovery module exposes an API. The details of the exposed REST endpoints are described next. Likewise, the endpoints consumed by the Intent-based Discovery module are also detailed in this section.

4.3.2.1 Exposed

The endpoints exposed by the Intent-based Discovery API are depicted in Figure 3-4.

Intent Based Discovery API 0.0.1 OAS 3.1

[/openapi.json](#)

Intent Based Discovery API for the DLT Marketplace

This API is the entry point of the Intent Based Discovery (IBD) system. It receives a raw intent written in natural language and returns a list of relevant offers from the DLT marketplace.

[Contact the developer](#)

Figure 3-4. Exposed OpenAPI of the Intent-based Discovery module

The three provided endpoints are explained below.

- POST /intent
 - This endpoint returns a set of offers registered in the Marketplace for a given intent. The expected parameters are:
 - *raw_intent*: A string representing an intent written in natural, or semi-natural intent.
 - *language*: A literal that only accepts two arguments: either *natural* or *semi-natural*. That way the Intent-based Discovery API knows whether the intent needs to go first through the LLM for a translation or not.
- GET /intent
 - Retrieves an intent object from the module database given an intent id.
- GET /intents
 - Retrieves all the intents available in the module database.

Consumed

As described before, the following three APIs of external components are consumed by the Intent-based Discovery module.

1. The LLM Client connects to ollama as the LLM server and then performs an HTTP POST request in the /api/generate endpoint. The payload only contains two attributes, which are model_name and prompt. The attribute model_name refers to the model that is going to process the prompt, in our case is by default intent_interpreter, because we built a fine-tuned model. The prompt attribute refers to the prompt itself in string format. Complete API documentation can be checked in [17].

2. The Cluster retrieval Client performs an HTTP request with arguments from the intent in the /intent_cluster_proximity endpoint of the Clustering and Classification module. This endpoint processes the arguments and returns the cluster ids corresponding to the identifiers of the related offer's clusters. The expected payload sent to the Clustering and Classification module follows the following scheme. Note that it has a generic structure in order to allow several key value attributes.

```
{
  "offer": [
    {
      "parameter_name": "cpu",
      "parameter_value": "3"
    }
  ],
  "offer_type": "cloud",
  "various_clusters": false
}
```

3. The DLT client connects to the Offering API in a specific IP and port and then makes a HTTP POST request in the /market/offer/cluster endpoint, passing a list of clusters_id obtained previously by the cluster retrieval client, following the schema depicted below. The clusters ids are passed in the JSON payload of the POST request in the clusters_id attribute. Then, the DLT returns a list of offers related to the initial intent that the user introduced.

```
{
  "clusters_id": [
    0
  ]
}
```

3.4 Deployment

The developed code for the Intent-based Discovery module is available in the project repository (hosted in Gitlab). In this section, the main deployment aspects to get this application running are provided.

3.4.1 Installation Procedures

First, it is needed to install the dependencies. These are related to the LLM server, the Clustering and Classification module and the Offering API.

- LLM server: Ollama can be easily install in Linux systems by running:

```
curl https://ollama.ai/install.sh | sh
```

Once it finishes, ollama will be running as a linux daemon. While this is enough to run LLMs, it is strongly recommended to run models using an Nvidia GPU. Otherwise, CPUs will be used, and processing times can be long. When running that command, ollama will install all the needed GPU drivers automatically. Just make sure that Nvidia GPU is detected by Linux. To check so, use the following command:

```
$ sudo lspci | grep NVIDIA
00:05.0 3D controller: NVIDIA Corporation TU104GL [Tesla T4] (rev a1)
```

In order to perform remote operations in the LLM server, it is needed to expose the ollama API. Ollama by default is exposing its API only in localhost at port 11434. In

order to expose the API outside of the machine, the following steps need to be performed:

- Create a *systemd* drop-in directory and set *Environment=OLLAMA_HOST*.
- Note that running with *sudo* does not work for some reason in Ubuntu. Make sure you log as root (e.g. *sudo su*)

```
sudo mkdir -p /etc/systemd/system/ollama.service.d
echo '[Service]' >>/etc/systemd/system/ollama.service.d/environment.conf
```

Then, continue with the following commands:

```
echo 'Environment="OLLAMA_HOST=0.0.0.0:11434"'
>>/etc/systemd/system/ollama.service.d/environment.conf
```

Finally, reload *systemd* and restart Ollama:

```
systemctl daemon-reload
systemctl restart ollama
```

- Clustering and Classification module: For the installation of this dependency, check the instructions provided in Section 2.4.1
- Offering API: The installation of this component of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace is detailed in its corresponding deliverable [18].

Once the dependencies are in place, the next step is to install the Intent-based Discovery module. The Intent-based Discovery module can be deployed directly running the Python application or inside containers, either in a Docker environment or a Kubernetes cluster.

- Using the python interpreter: For running the intent-based discovery API directly using the python interpreter, first it is recommended to create a virtual environment:

```
$ virtualenv .venv
```

Then, install the needed dependencies using pip.

```
$ pip3 install -r requirements.txt
```

Then, make sure the dotenv file is properly configured with the appropriate configuration.

Finally, the application can be executed running the following command from the root of the project directory.

```
$ python -m ibd.main
```

- Using Docker: To run the application as a container using docker a docker compose and Dockerfile files are provided.

To use them just run the following command. This will pull the image from the docker registry from the latest default branch. Also, the image can be manually built from the provided Dockerfile.

```
$ docker compose up
```

- Using Kubernetes: For Kubernetes, a helm chart is provided for ease of deployment. The helm chart consists of a service and a deployment. They look as follows.

- Helm Kubernetes Deployment

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: {{.Values.name}}
  namespace: {{.Values.namespace}}
  labels:
    app: {{.Values.name}}
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: {{.Values.name}}
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: {{.Values.name}}
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: {{.Values.name}}
          image: {{.Values.image}}
          imagePullPolicy: {{.Values.imagePullPolicy}}
          ports:
            - containerPort: {{.Values.port}}
      imagePullSecrets:
        - name: gitlab-token-registry
      restartPolicy: Always
      nodeName: {{.Values.nodeName}}
```

Note that it requires a *gitlab-token-registry* secret that contains a token to be able to pull from the container registry located in a private GitLab instance.

- Helm Kubernetes Service

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: {{.Values.serviceName}}
  namespace: {{.Values.namespace}}
spec:
```

```

selector:
  app: {{.Values.name}}
  type: {{.Values.type}}
ports:
  - port: {{.Values.port}}
    targetPort: {{.Values.port}}
    nodePort: {{.Values.nodePort}}

```

The helm deploys a Kubernetes service, exposing the service in the IP of the cluster (mode NodePort).

The intent-based discovery can be deployed in a Kubernetes cluster simply by running helm. From the root of the project, run the following command.

```
$ helm install intent-based-discovery-api helm/intent-based-discovery
```

3.4.2 User Documentation

The easiest way to get started using the Intent-based Discovery module is to run the application and then access the Uniform Resource Locator (URL) where it's deployed using a browser. By default, it will show the OpenAPI user interface. To test for instance the POST /intent endpoint as shown in Figure 3-5, just press the *try it out* button and write the intent.

Figure 3-5. Example of use for the POST /intent endpoint

For a quick test, we can use the following intents:

- Semi-natural intent: discover offers for offer_type=cloud with memory=2, cpu=3, storage=500, location=Madrid, price=300
- Natural intent: I want a cloud offer with 4 CPU and 8 GB of RAM, located in Madrid, that costs 300 and would like it to be sorted by price.

This request will return a set of offers of type cloud meeting the criteria specified in the intent.

3.4.3 Integration Guideline

This module has integration points with the SCSC, the Clustering and Classification module and the Offering API for the following purposes:

- Integration with the SCSC: When a discovery request is submitted to the Marketplace, this is received by the SCSC, which forwards it to the Intent-based Discovery module of the Smart Discovery system. In particular, the SCSC consumes the POST /intent endpoint exposed by this module API, which decipher the received intent, retrieve the cluster ID(s) corresponding to the requested offer type and characteristics and then retrieve the set of offers that belong to the given cluster(s).
- Integration with the Clustering and Classification module: This is an interaction internal to the operational flows of the Smart Discovery system. It is used to map the translated intent to the cluster(s) that best reflect the characteristics of the offer indicated in the intent.
- Integration with the Offering API: To retrieve the set of offers for the identified cluster(s) the Intent-based Discovery module relies on the Offer API. In particular, the DLT client of this module consumes the /market/offer/cluster endpoint of the Offering API, passing it a list of clusters_id obtained previously from the Clustering and Classification module. This integration results in the retrieval of existing offers classified within the corresponding clusters ID.

3.5 Results and Next Steps

With the current deployment we are able to:

- Interpret semi-natural and natural intents.
- Retrieve offers stored in a distributed database based on DLT.

As we look forward to the future, there are several improvements for further enhancement of the Intent-based Discovery. Here are some potential areas of focus:

- Improved Language Models. While our current LLM has shown effectiveness, there is room for improvement. Investigate fine-tuning strategies to enhance overall performance.
- Investigate more for a lightweight NLP approach tailored for our use case. Explore the development of a more lightweight NLP approach specifically tailored to our use case. This could involve streamlining processes, optimizing algorithms, or adopting new techniques that align with the project's requirements. LLMs are good, but they are quite heavy and performance demanding. In order to scale well, probably we need to go for a more lightweight approach such as NLP.
- Close-loop integration with intent database. Consider implementing a closed-loop system for utilizing the intent database to fine-tune the language models. This iterative process can lead to more accurate and context-aware responses, enhancing the overall system's adaptability.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the deliverable represents a significant milestone in the 6GENABLERS-DLT project's journey towards redefining Telecom Marketplaces. Through meticulous design, implementation, and documentation, this deliverable lays the foundation for implementing the prototype of the Smart Discovery system that addresses the intricate challenges posed by evolving network landscapes.

The prototype implementation of the Smart Discovery system demonstrates our commitment to enhancing the efficiency of Telecom Marketplaces by providing a robust mechanism for categorizing and organizing network resources, while adapting to user needs dynamically. The prototype is composed of two modules, namely: Clustering and Classification and Intent-based Discovery.

In essence, the Clustering and Classification module stands as a cornerstone in the realization of an intelligent, user-centric Telecom Marketplace. Its functionalities are intricately designed to streamline the categorization and identification processes, contributing significantly to the overall success of the Smart Discovery system within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

Similarly, the Intent-based Discovery module serves as a sophisticated interpreter, translating user desires into actionable insights within the structured framework of the Telecom Marketplace. Its capabilities extend beyond mere translation, orchestrating a seamless journey from understanding user intent to presenting a tailored selection of offerings.

The architecture, functionalities, and deployment strategies detailed in this document collectively form a comprehensive toolkit for automated discovery. This toolkit is poised to empower stakeholders, from equipment vendors to application developers, with the means to seamlessly engage with and benefit from the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

As we reflect on the journey undertaken in this deliverable, it becomes evident that the path to resilient Telecom Marketplaces demands a synergistic blend of technological innovation and user-centric design. The challenges of complexity, privacy, and trust have been acknowledged and addressed through the integration of resilient distributed Marketplaces and the judicious use of automation methods.

Looking forward, the insights gained from this prototype implementation pave the way for further refinement and advancements. The lessons learned will inform subsequent iterations, ensuring that the operational components and toolkit for automated discovery continue to evolve in tandem with the dynamic landscape of telecommunications.

In essence, E5.2 marks not just the culmination of a phase but the commencement of a trajectory towards more adaptive, responsive, and user-friendly Telecom Marketplaces. The commitment to excellence and innovation demonstrated in this deliverable reinforces our dedication to shaping the future of distributed ledger technology within the telecommunications domain. As we embark on the next stages of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, we anticipate building upon this foundation to realize a Marketplace that truly reflects the diverse and evolving needs of our stakeholders.

5 References

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